

AREAL SPECIFICITY IN SOCIAL DIALECTICISMS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10109996>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 04th November 2023

Accepted: 10th November 2023

Online: 11th November 2023

KEY WORDS

Social lexicon, social dialecticism, sectoral lexicon, lexicalization, dialectics related to childbirth.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses social lexicon, its types, social-household lexicon. The article analyzes of social dialectics and their territorial-areal peculiarities have been carried out. Examples of social dialectics of Sariosia district of Surkhandarya region are given and explained.

It is known that in scientific and educational literature we often find terms such as sociality, social dialect, social dialectisms. Usually, social dialects are such a form of language that they do not correspond to the literary language and its norms. However, in many sources, there are views of social dialects as tools that reveal one or another aspect of the literary language.

Social dialects are a lexicon that forms a certain layer of the national language. They are words related to the activities of individuals belonging to a certain stratum. In this regard, scientists such as V. Zhirmunsky, B. Serebrennikov, and V. Avorin conducted research in Russian linguistics, and the researches of S. Ibragimov, E. Begmatov, A. Sobirov, and D. Abdurakhmanov in Uzbek linguistics are noteworthy.

There are many opinions about the definition of social lexicon. In particular, B. Serebrennikov mentions that they are not dialects, but variants of social speech, speech styles. At the same time, recognizing that these speech variants serve as social dialects, he notes their phonetic system and grammatical construction. So, social dialects, both as variants of social speech and as speech styles, differ from the literary language in phonetic, lexical, and grammatical terms. That is why thinking in this matter is carried out in a certain sense based on one or another justification of the social lifestyle.

Social dialects of a given language serve for individuals belonging to different groups of people. Their social origin, customs, traditions, professions are important in revealing various aspects. Of course, social dialects (literary language, regional dialects, spoken language) are inextricably linked with certain language forms.

In Uzbek linguistics, the lexicon of fields is one of the branches that have been studied to a certain extent. Many candidacy and doctoral theses have been defended in this field¹. In the Uzbek language, the words related to the sectoral lexicon, in particular, the names of clothes and their parts, were specially studied².

In the modern Uzbek literary language, the household-social lexicon has been studied as a separate object of comparative-historical, lexical-semantic research. In the research conducted by L.Kh. Gafurov, the household lexicon of the Uzbek language was first divided into the following lexical-semantic groups and analyzed: "names of kitchen items", "names of beds", names of hygiene items, household appliances names", names of housing construction", "names of lighting equipment", names of household appliances", "names of heating and cooling devices", "names of communication equipment".

An interesting aspect of areal linguistic research is that the lexicon of peoples speaking the same language is used differently in different regions. Surkhandarya oasis is one of the regions with such a wide lexical layer. The units representing the household lexicon used in the speech of Surkhandarya people are quite different from the lexicon of people living in other regions of our republic. For example: dialectal lexemes such as names of household items, names of clothes, names of jewelry and ornaments, names of food, names of agricultural products are characteristic of the speech of Uzbeks living in the neighborhoods and villages of Surkhandarya. Some of these words are influenced by the Tajik language (*tuzdon-namakdon, bolish-bolisht, do'ppi-toqqi, nimcha-gupicha, beshbarmoq-ko'lova*), while others are formed based on phonetic differences (*cholop-chalop, qatlama-qalama, yostiq-astiq*).

It is known that the lexical system of any language includes all lexical units, stable language combinations, phraseologisms and lexicalized elements that exist in that language. Usually, the lexical structure of the language in scientific literature means lexical units that exist only in the literary language, lexical tools of the language related to the norms of the literary language. The lexical composition of the Uzbek language includes lexical-semantic units that are not only included in the lexicon of the literary language, but also belong to the lexicon of the national Uzbek language, dialects, dialects. These two lexical layers, i.e. the literary language and the national language, the lexical layers of dialects, dialects, were always in contact with each other, connected to each other and complementing each other, constantly moving lexical layers. Their mutual influence is evident in their mutual enrichment, adaptation to the times, improvement and development of the internal structure of the language, stabilization and standardization of the necessary language tools.

From this point of view, the language tools of the national language in all regions, lexical units of branches, various terms related to fields are of great importance for the development of the literary language and for the development of the science of linguistics. Although the

¹ Muhammadiyeva M. The issue of mapping socio-household lexicon in area linguistic research. Mag. diss. – Termiz 2023. Mamatov N. Uzbekskaya khlopkovodcheskaya terminology: Autoref. dis. ... candy. Philol. Nauk. - Tashkent, 1955. - 16 p.; Ibragimov S. Professionalnaya lexika Uzbekskigo yazika (na materialakh ferganskikh govorov): Autoref. dis. ...Dr Philol. Nauk. - Tashkent, 1961. - 163; Abdiev M. System analysis of field lexicon (based on materials of professions of Samarkand region): Philol. Doctor of Sciences...dis. - Tashkent, 2004. - 262 p.

² Asomutdinova M. Names of clothes and their parts in Uzbek: Filol. Candidate of Sciences ... diss. - Tashkent, 1970.

names characteristic of the lexicon of fields in Uzbek linguistics have been studied to date, they have not been widely studied from an area point of view. In particular, although certain types of social lexicon have been studied within the Surkhandarya region, social dialectics and their areal classification have not been fully studied. Therefore, the research of the social lexicon from the dialectal and areal point of view is one of the linguistic problems that are still waiting for a solution.

When studying the vocabulary of the language as a system, it is important to rely on the hypo-hyperonymic relations of lexemes: it is important to understand the meanings of lexemes, which are the names of things in nature and society, and through these meanings, the things in existence. allows to generalize and differentiate the concepts and ideas about themselves³.

Therefore, it is appropriate to study the names of household items in the Uzbek language as a system, and they can be divided into the following lexical-semantic groups:

- a) names of household items related to the kitchen;
- b) names of household appliances;
- c) names of household items related to the economy. These groups are further divided into smaller groups and they also indicate the types of household items.

Analyzing the names of household items in the language of the Uzbeks of the Sariosia district of the Surkhandarya region, determining their place and position within the Uzbek national language, their relation to the variants in the literary language or researching only the dialectal variants of these names - the Uzbek version of these names helps to determine the position in the lexical system of the language. The studied area is distinguished by its variety of household items in Uzbek dialects: for example, *so'zan*, *igna-iyna*, *tavar-tabar*, *bel*, *belcha*, *ketmon*, *chovidish*, *ketmoncha*, *qaychi*, *bigiz*, *qayroq*, *urchuq*, *o'ymoq*, *angisht o'rmak*, *o'roq-dost*, *bolta*, *shoxa*, *chaykun*, *kelchak tosh*, *chovgum*, *zog'no'l* etc.

We will study the names of household and household items mentioned above, divided into the following groups:

1. Names of working tools;
2. Names of household items used in sewing;
3. Names of various types of household items related to the economy. The names of household items used in Sariasia Uzbek dialects have their own practical significance.

The observation of the dialect lexicon shows that the traditions of social development, population integration and globalization are developing. As a result, words representing many concepts and objects are falling out of use. At the same time, there are many traditions and social customs in human society. For this reason, social strata or ethnographies in the lexicon of Surkhandarya dialects are of great importance. We will discuss them below. In Uzbek traditions, there are stable combinations such as rocking the cradle and giving white milk in some cases. Such integrated devices are directly the result of our customs and traditions, that is, it is a great responsibility to respect the parents who brought up and brought up in the Uzbek people, and to please them⁴.

³ Ne'matov H., Rasulov R. Fundamentals of the system lexicology of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1995.

⁴ Jorakhanova.S.A. Taboo and euphemisms in lexemes expressing tradition. –Scientific Journal Impact Factor: 2022.

The history of traditions goes back to the creation of mankind. At first, there were no religious concepts in the primitive society. Traditions were created on the basis of people's work and had a great impact on the development of society and the growth of people's consciousness. It is known that the development of a person starts from his infancy, and every nation, according to its custom, holds various ceremonies and ceremonies as soon as a child is born.

According to folklorist O. Safarov, "In the presence of midwives, nannies and grooms, special ceremonies are held when a baby is baptized, cradled for the first time, when the first tooth comes out, when the first hair is cut, when the first step is taken, when the first nail is cut."⁵ Although these ceremonies are called differently in different regions, they have one lexical-semantic commonality. For example, ethnographic terms such as *umbilical cord cutting*, *seven chilla*, *twenty chilla*, *forty chilla*, *cradle* are still actively used in Sariosia district of Surkhandarya region.

Cradling - This ritual of cradling a baby is performed by old women. The following crib accessories are prepared for this ceremony.

Bolishcha – a pillow to be placed under the baby's feet;

Lo'lapech – cloth to wrap and swaddle a baby;

Dastband – a cradle made of fabric to bind the baby's hand;

Poband – a cloth used to bind a baby's feet. In addition, accessories such as *nayak* and *siva* are also installed in the crib according to the rules, and the young mother is taught the rules of cradling the baby.

The originality of the dialects of Sariosia can be found in all spheres of speech of the representatives of the dialect. Most of the ethnographic units representing farm and livelihood tools found in Sariosia Uzbek dialects have commonalities, as in other Uzbek dialects⁶.

These are: *xig* – is a piece of goatskin made of goatskin, which is mainly used to separate sweet yogurt from whey. *O'xloq*, *kafkir* (*qirg'ich* – Variant in the village of Dashnabad, Sariosia district), *nonpar* (*chekich* – In Dashnabad dialect), *rafida*, *surpa*, *siyxak* etc. These ethnographic units are common to all Uzbek dialects and almost all have the same lexical-semantic features.

Another feature of the terms representing household tools is that some of them have a completely different appearance, but although they are named differently, they have the same concept and meaning lexically-semantically and grammatically. For example, *lalicha-tarelka*, *la'li-lagan*, *supra-surpa*, *jo'va-o'xlovcha* etc.

In short, the social, household-social lexicon has a lot of specific, researched features. In particular, social dialectics are territorially diverse and colorful. There is no doubt that considering each of them separately on the linguistic level and carrying out analyzes will serve the development of the field of linguistics.

⁵ Safarov O. Children's caressing folk songs. Tashkent - Science, 1982.

⁶ Muhammadiyeva M. The issue of social-household lexicon mapping in areal linguistic research. Mag. diss. - Termiz 2023. - B:85.

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